

Artificial Machine Intelligence Conversation in Digital Marketing through Chatbots

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ABSTRACT

Chatbots are intelligent machines serving digital visitors. Intelligent machines are capable of simulating knowledge. This paper examines some of the latest AI patterns and activities then provides alternative theory of change in some of the popular and widely accepted postulates of today. Based on AI (Artificial Intelligence) structuring and NLP (Natural language Processing) based software, chatbots are made. The paper highlights that AI is ever improving and sheds light on the potential of machine intelligence and NLP tasks. The rise of chatbots in digital marketing is the latest disruptive force that led to a change in customer interaction. In the context of digital markets and digital services, the emergence of AI driven chatbots has changed the phase of interaction among digital customers. The marketing sector plays an important role in development into any country. It also explores the usability of chatbots to assess whether it can fulfill digital customers ever-changing needs.

Keywords: Chatbot, AI, NLP, AMIC, digital markets.

1. INTRODUCTION

Digital Marketing use technology to deliver products or services. Since the competitor is technology based in digital business, it can hail from any segment. Artificial intelligence (AI) has impacted in our day-to-day activities by designing and evaluating advanced applications and devices called intelligent machines capable of simulating knowledge which can perform various functions. Chatbots are intelligent machines designed to simulate conversation with human users in natural language especially over the internet. A chatbot is a human computer interaction model which only represents the natural evolution of a Question Answering system leveraging Natural Language Processing (NLP) and sentiment analysis. Hence Artificial Machine Intelligence communication (AMIC) has been recognized as one of the central enablers of digital business transformation in several industries leveraging digital technologies to create or modify customer experiences and culture, and business processes, thus meeting customers ever changing needs and the market strategy.

Building AMIC capabilities: Pattern Recognition Understanding trends in transactions and spot deviations to identify potentially fraudulent behaviour.

Prediction: To capture short and long term variability in data to improve forecasting. Cognitive Search: Offer personalized recommendations to Shoppers by matching their interests with other customers who purchased similar items,

Natural Language Interaction: Will ask a software application to generate a report on sales revenue predictions without having to run the reports,

Natural Language Generation: To obtain summaries of everything that has been analysed from a large document collection.

Role of AMIC in Digital Workforce: It will help by automating repetitive tasks or processes with robotic process automation(RPA).

Onboarding: Covers onboarding of new employees and customers. Once the customers are enrolled, using machine intelligence technology can track and learn from this customers behaviour to let a company offer tailored services.

Accounts payable and invoice processing: Automating invoices and applying robotic process automation(RPA) offers more intelligence to accounts payable.

Artificial Intelligence help to take staff better decisions with the use of graphical dashboards.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW:

Artificial Intelligence: AI is revolutionizing digital business due to its ability to make data-based decisions quickly and accurately. With Customer relationship management (CRM) AI technology can maximize the collection of user information from different platforms, gain accurate insights for target customers and identify users' needs so that companies can determine the most appropriate marketing strategy.

Chatbots: How a Chatbot Works: The ability to identify the user's intent and extract data and relevant entities contained in the user's request is the first condition and the most relevant step at the core of a chatbot: If we are not able to correctly understand the user's request, you won't be able to provide the correct answer. Once the user's intent has been identified, the chatbot must provide the most appropriate response for the user's request.

Chatbot applications streamline interactions between people and services, enhancing customer experience. At the same time, they offer companies new opportunities to improve the customers engagement process and operational efficiency by reducing the typical cost of customer service. To be successful, a chatbot solution should be able to effectively perform both of these tasks.

Chatbots In Marketing:

Chatbots can answer repeated questions and they do this efficiently, thus, saving time, money and resources we spend on handling these queries. Chatbots improve customer service and do it by being available 24/7, replying to queries in no time, and reducing typing efforts. chatbots use a clever method to expand the audience by capturing the data of the user who contact them on chat.

Chatbots eliminate errors as they don't forget things, they work on pre-written commands, and always do what they're programmed for. Hence, they don't commit mistakes. Chatbots drive customers and convert them into buyers by suggesting the right products they want to buy. This eliminates product browsing, thus, eases their buying journey.

Few examples of innovative use of chatbots in India.

CarDekho Gaadi store is a retail auction model for pre-owned cars where Users can now directly book an appointment for checking maximum car valuation with Gaadi bot in just 2 minutes. Gaadi bot makes conversation in "Hinglish" (Hindi in English alphabets).

iPAL Chatbot (ICICI Bank) can assist ICICI with basic banking needs with just voice commands can guide on how to apply for loans and credit cards and also updates with the account balance whenever asked.

Karl chatbot has become a tool for **Jeep-India** to increase their customer base in the automobile market which assist with the nearest dealer or service center and saves human resources that spend on customer assistance.

TIA Chatbot (Tata Capital) is a Tata Financial and Investment services subsidiary. Being and helps users in wealth management which provides an easy and interactive EMI calculator.

Travel Planner Chatbot (Travel Triangle) is one of the best travel assistance chatbots in India assisting users with hotels, flights, and private cabs pricing and availability for travel, help in planning trips and can prefer the best season for traveling to any place. They provides better filters than any other travel assistance chatbot like "Trip for solo", "Family trip", "Trip with friends", etc.

Disha Chatbot (PathKind Labs) is helping path kind labs to provide faster services like booking an appointment and getting reports online. Reduces crowd from work-place and call queues by offering online reports and necessary details through the chatbot. Helps in finding the nearest PathKind Labs, and collection center.

Eva (HDFC Bank) HDFC Bank is India's largest private bank and EVA chatbot is the first and largest banking chatbot in India. With continuous learning, EVA Chatbot has assisted users on more than 1.2 million queries !!

ABG Assistant (Aditya Birla Group) **Aditya Birla Group** is India's 3rd largest private conglomerate with more than 30 subsidiaries. and their website also has ABG Assistant Chatbot. This chatbot works like a navigator which can navigate visitors at whichever page they want to go. It doesn't have abilities like other chatbots but is unique. that has respectfully welcoming skills, which creates a positive impression on the visitor.

Programming languages used in chatbots:

Java has its capability to create high-level features, an object-oriented programming language, the portability of Java makes it ideal for **Chatbot** development and excellent for easily coding algorithms with advanced features.

Clojure is a programming language used for general purposes and allows access to several Java frameworks and language is considered as part of the Lisp family of language. and considered easy to use because of the higher-order functions instead of the side-effect-based looping.

Python regarded as the most widely used programming language for building **Chatbots** and is simply because Python is equipped with AIML or Artificial Intelligence Markup Language, which makes it extremely easier to compose syntax for complex Chatbot features. Natural language processing (NLP) toolkit, which is a key element of intelligent chatbots is written by Python.

For AI based Chatbot development, speed and performance has come as an additional advantage in C++, a stable language that can quickly build a sophisticated app with Machine Learning and the development of the neural network. AI-powered Chatbot algorithms can be written fully with C++.

With PHP building chatbot is cheap as the language is completely open-source and extremely easy to use ,as a high-level scripting language, it can be used to build Chatbot at a much lower cost.

Ruby is another powerful and high-level programming language that can make your job of building Chatbot effortless and easy. Also an object-oriented programming language and the language also comes well equipped with all the tools you require for building a sophisticated Chatbot.

Lisp is one of the oldest high-level programming languages that went through multi-layered evolution to become a highly efficient and dynamic language, it has been widely used by developers to build intelligent and conversational Chatbots of all types.

Vernacular Chatbot:

Dhee Yantra

This Bangalore-based **chatbot** startup uses AI and NLP to provide a multilingual conversation platform for businesses. Apart from English, the bot also supports other Indian languages like Hindi, Kannada, Telugu, Malayalam, Marathi, Gujarati and Bangla. Its aim is to help businesses to reach out to the Indian native-speaking community.

Robotic Process Automation(RPA):RPA applies software robots or bots, to automate repetitive processes at scale, eliminating inefficiencies, cutting costs, and improving speed and performance and focuses on eliminating manual or human involvement in process steps.

Chatbots are generally conversation-driven processes that are user-centric whereas RPA is applicable to specific discrete workflows that don't even require a user interaction (by using screen-scraping and data extraction).

Key components of a conversational chatbot architecture:

Environment

This is where the core Natural Language Process (NLP) engine and context interpretation happens.

NLP Engine

NLP Engine is the core component which interprets. **NLP engine** contains advanced machine learning algorithms to identify the user's intent and further matches them to the list of available intents the bot supports.

NLP Engine further has two components:

Intent Classifier: Intent classifier takes user's input identifies its meaning and relates back to one of the intents that the chatbot supports.

Entity Extractor: Entity extractor is what extracts key information from the user's query.

Agent for Dialogue Management

It manages the actual context of the dialogue. For example, the user might say "He needs to order pizza" and the bot might take the order. Then the user might say "Change it to ice-cream", here the user refers to the order he has placed earlier, the bot must correctly interpret this and make changes to the order he has placed earlier before confirming with the user.

Dialog management plugin enables us to do this.

Dialogue management further has following key plugins:

Feedback Mechanism: Here the agent takes the feedback from user time to time to learn if the bot is doing fine with the conversation and the user is satisfied with the bot's response which further reinforces the bot to learn from mistakes and corrects itself in future conversations.

- **Policy Learning:** Policy learning is a higher-level framework that creates the network

of happy paths and routes the conversation to end-user satisfaction. The bot then tries to learn from the interactions and follows the interaction flow about the conversation it had with similar users in the past.

Question and Answer System

The key component in answering users' FAQs (frequently asked questions). Q & A system interprets the question and responds with relevant answers from the knowledge base. It has the following components

- **Manual Training:** Manual training involves the domain expert creating the list of frequently asked users queries and map its answers. This helps the bot quickly identify the answers to the most important questions.
- **Automated Training:** Automated training involves submitting the company's documents like policy documents and other Q&A type of documents to the bot and ask it to train itself. The engine comes up with a list of question and answers from these documents. The bot will be able to answer with confidence.

. Plugins/Components

Plugins offer chatbots solution APIs and other **automation** components for chatbots used for internal company use like HR management and **field-worker** chatbots.

. Node Server / Traffic Server

The Node server that handles the traffic requests from users and routes them to appropriate components and also routes the response from internal components back to the front-end systems.

. Front-End Systems

Front-end systems can be any client-facing platforms or the actual chatbot interfaces that reside in various platforms like:

- Facebook
- Slack
- Google Hangouts
- Skype for Business
- Microsoft Teams

Conversational AI platform:

The users interact with chatbots through the messenger interface and Messenger API provides the following rich functionality:

Posting content — support for text, images, files, and structured templates that provide a consistent experience across bots

- Delivered callbacks — a bot can detect that a user has received messages
 - Receiving content — a bot can access messages that the user inputs in the chat with the bot
 - A rich set of predefined button actions, including Buy, Share, Call, URL, and Postback (to send an action to your bot)
 - Quick Replies that provide the user canned responses to questions
 - Opening a web view for custom out-of-Messenger interaction
 - Sending geo-location information with a single click
- Understanding The Role Of Sentiment Analysis In Chatbots

Chatbot technology has had an undeniable impact on digital marketing, customer experience, in particular. When we talk about Artificial machine intelligence conversational in AI-based applications for augmenting customer and employee experience, chatbots emerge as a front-runner. With the advancements in AI and **machine learning**, chatbots have become more powerful and incorporated new features that helped improve user experience and these latest features that is taking user experience to the next level is sentiment analysis. Sentiment analysis is a sub field of machine learning and **natural language processing** that deals with extracting thoughts, opinions, or sentiments from voice or textual data. It is currently widely used in marketing and customer service functions to analyse customer data from surveys, social media and reviews. This not only enables digital businesses to understand the impact of their products/services but also to tweak their strategies as per the end customers' opinion. In the context of chatbots, sentiment analysis helps a chatbot to understand the emotions and state of mind of the users by analyzing their input text or voice. and in developing the bot's emotional intelligence. While machine learning helps to personalize the chatbot's performance by harnessing historical customer data, NLP helps to evaluate and interpret the information sent by the customer in real-time.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The main research question is: How artificial machine intelligence conversation has use to chatbots and has impacted the digital marketing ? The rapid increase in the deployment of "artificial machine intelligence", has transformed the business scene permanently. Customers regularly interact with automated devices that help them to serve their needs themselves . Chatbots play essential roles in the digital marketing landscape and other fields. This study make known to the readers the usage and methods employed in chatbots . The study also reviews all the qualitative data used for this research paper to reach a credible conclusion.

4. DISCUSSIONS:

Although, all of the programming languages mentioned in this study have a robust capacity to build the most sophisticated and powerful AI Chatbots, not all of them equally fits into various requirements. Naturally, the selection of the language will ultimately depend upon the project features and constraints.

5. CONCLUSIONS:

Artificial Machine Intelligence Conversation will move towards a stage in the economy where digital products will be increasingly intelligent to make recommendations, present options, and

help customers make their choices. In every debate of Artificial Machine Intelligence conversation, **chatbots** have become the most popular subheading of it. With the increase in chatbots use cases, digital marketing are seeing an uptick in their customer support and lead generation. Law firms, Banks, Healthcare organizations, Automobile industry, Government sector etc., are upgrading themselves with a chatbot for primary uses like assisting, inquiring, booking, filtering, etc.

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